



Figure S1. *Maietta (Hoffeinsonera) christelae*, n. sp., Baltic amber: A, habitus; B, thorax (A, anepisternum; Am, anepimeron; K, katepisternum; Km, katepimeron; M, meron). *Maietta (Maietta) trimedia* Alexander, recent species: C, SEM photograph of thorax.